

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF PREPARING STUDENTS FOR CREATIVE ACTIVITY BASED ON FOREIGN EXPERIENCES

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Annotatsiya This article provides information on the use of foreign experiences in education to positively influence the educational process of students. In recent years, in the educational system of the leading foreign countries, special and serious attention has been paid to the issue of formation of creativity in pupils and students.

Key words: foreign experience, opinion of scientists, creativity skills.

In recent years, in the educational system of leading foreign countries, special and serious attention has been paid to the issue of forming the qualities of creativity in pupils and students. Bronson, Merryman (2010), Ken Robinson (2007), Fisher, Frey (2008), Begetto, Kaufman (2013), Ali (2011), Treffinger (2008), and b. many studies conducted by, can be seen from their results.

According to Patti Drapeau, creative thinking is, first of all, comprehensive thinking about a specific issue. Multidisciplinary thinking requires students to rely on multiple ideas when completing assignments, problems, and tasks. In contrast, one-sided thinking is based on only one correct idea. In observation, it is impossible to deny one of the one-sided and multi-sided thinking on the issue. Therefore, one and all-round thinking is equally important in the formation of creativity. That is, when completing a task, solving a problem, the student looks for several options for a solution (multi-sided thinking), and then stops at one correct solution that guarantees the most optimal result (unilateral thinking). Patti Drapeau “If you think you're not creative, I suggest that you start organizing creative thinking classes right now. In fact, it's not about whether or not you are creative and creative, but about organizing classes in the spirit of creativity and striving to try new ideas in practice," he says [1].

According to Ken Robinson, "creativity is a set of original ideas that have their own value." And Gardner explains the concept in his research: "creativity is a practical action performed by a person, which should reflect a certain novelty and have a certain practical value." Based on the above-mentioned ideas, the concept of "creativity" can be interpreted as follows: creativity (lat., ing. "create" - creation, "creative" - creator) - describes the readiness of an individual to produce new ideas and is an independent factor in the composition of talent according to E.P. Torrens, the concept of "creativity" covers the following [2]:

- to put forward a problem or scientific hypothesis;
- checking and changing the hypothesis; - identifying the problem based on the formation of decision results;

- sensitivity to the conflict between knowledge and practical actions in finding a solution to a problem. As already mentioned, creative qualities do not develop in pedagogues as in all individuals. According to this research, a number of ways to successfully develop creative qualities in a person (including pedagogues) are highlighted. Patti Drepeau also suggests four ways to successfully develop creativity in individuals (including educators):

- Formation of creative thinking skills.
- Development of practical creative movement skills.
- Organization of creative activity processes.
- Use of creative products (developments).

The essence of these roads will be discussed below.

Way 1: formation of creative thinking skills. In this, the main emphasis is on the formation of creative thinking skills, and learners are directed to express the essence of creative actions with the help of verbs. In particular, in order to effectively form the skills of creative thinking, teachers pay attention to the presence of necessary verbs in the questions that encourage students to think. If this situation is explained with examples, the control question "describe the relationship between the heart and blood circulation system" from the learners does not form their creativity. After all,

the concept of "describe" in the question is equivalent to saying "tell your existing knowledge one by one".

Using words (verbs) that encourage students to think when asking control questions facilitates their creative thinking. Therefore, according to the first way of forming creative qualities in a person, it is appropriate for pedagogues to use words (verbs) that force different, antique, unconventional and thorough answers. For example, the use of words (verbs) such as "find a connection", "create", "predict", "explain an idea logically", "imagine" is considered effective from a practical point of view. Instead of asking learners to "describe the relationship between the heart and the circulatory system," the teacher should ask them to "state all kinds of relationships between the heart and the circulatory system." must As a result, learners will have the opportunity to generalize existing knowledge and to put forward new thoughts and ideas.

It is appropriate for pedagogues to use the first method - to use the "Creativity Map" of young teachers in the formation of creativity skills in students.

Way 2: development of practical creative thinking skills. Educators use instructional methods and methods to form and develop creative thinking skills in students. In this case, the use of questions can only help in the short term, but it does not develop interactivity and engagement in learners. In her work, Patti Drapeau presents a number of ways and methods that are effective in developing interactivity and creative thinking skills in learners. In particular: - Working with websites; - visualization; - taking into account all points of view; - appropriate application of important ideas in different situations (transferring the idea to another situation - transformation); - such ways as symbolization; - "Brainstorming"; - Methods such as "Case-study".

Way 3: organization of creative activity processes. This path emphasizes creative, creative thinking in the process of solving problems and promoting innovative ideas. Although creative methods and methods are not actively used in these processes, creative thinking occurs. While completing the task, students analyze

various problems related to the human circulatory system. As a result, multifaceted thinking and observation takes place in this process.

4th way: use of creative products (developments). In this way, the pedagogue can give students the task of creating a presentation using Power Point or multimedia. Students actively develop creative thinking skills during the preparation of the presentation. Learners can fully express their creative thinking skills in a comfortable environment. If learners have a feeling of fear of failure, if they hesitate to express their thoughts incorrectly, if they face criticism, in such a situation, it will not be possible for them to effectively form or develop creative thinking skills. It is possible to successfully form the skill of creative thinking only by turning creativity into a habit in learners. In this process, the methods and tools used by them in the assessment of their thorough understanding of the content of the subject and creative thinking skills are of great importance.

Certain factors prevent the development of creative qualities and skills of pedagogues. Therefore, in the pedagogical process, teachers should focus on eliminating these factors. The following factors hinder the development of creativity in a person:

- 1) avoiding risk;
- 2) allow rudeness in thinking and behavior;
- 3) underestimation of personal fantasy and imagination;
- 4) subordination to others;

5) thinking only about success in any case. The creative potential of the teacher is reflected as his general characteristic. It is the first condition and result of creative activity. This quality represents a person's ability and readiness to express himself. In addition, on the basis of creative potential, the personal abilities, natural and social strength of each specialist are manifested as a whole. Creative potential is closely related to creativity focused on the cognitive process. The creative potential of a teacher, in contrast to traditional thinking, is manifested in the following:

- speed and flexibility of thinking;
- the ability to create new ideas;

- not thinking in one way;
- originality;
- initiative;
- tolerating uncertainty.

Self-development and self-expression of each pedagogue is directly related to his creativity. Usually, the ability of pedagogues to be creative is ensured by striving to solve pedagogical problems, carrying out scientific research or scientific projects, and achieving mutual creative cooperation.

Stages of formation of a creative person:

1st stage: mastering the theoretical and methodological foundations of such disciplines as pedagogy, psychology, philosophy, aesthetics.

Stage 2: Formation of the skills of practical application of acquired theoretical knowledge during continuous and continuous pedagogical practice, as well as during practical training and independent education.

Stage 3: To achieve the transformation of practical skills into qualifications based on independent study and creative research.

4th stage Psychological preparation for effective organization of professional activity based on existing theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications. The effective organization of professional activity by the teacher in these forms depends on the level of his creativity. Creative thinking can be clearly reflected in every social sphere. The teacher's creativity is reflected in his creative approach to the organization of professional activities organized by him.

The development of creativity in students requires the appropriate organization of the teaching process, depending on the level of knowledge, level of mastery, source of education, didactic tasks of students in mastering educational content. It is assumed that the following pedagogical conditions must be followed:

- to create a comfortable opportunity for students to think creatively, to accept various opinions and ideas expressed by students with tolerance and to ensure their activity in the educational process, to establish confidence in each student's ability to think creatively, regular stimulation of their creative activities;

- individualization of the educational process based on the characteristics, needs and intellectual potential of the student; to form students' individual, small group and teamwork skills, to expand their creative capabilities, to encourage them to accept non-standard solutions along with ready-made standard solutions in solving problems;

- selection and implementation of interactive training forms and methods that allow to practically re-develop and improve cognitive knowledge, which is the basis of creative activity development.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that it is necessary to systematically study the pedagogical needs, interests, directions of special importance of students, in which it is necessary to define effective ways to eliminate the countersuggestive, thesaurus and interactional barriers encountered in the organization of their creative activity.. Also, organizing the teaching process on the basis of ideas, concepts and advanced pedagogical experiences that serve to satisfy the creative interests and needs of students serves to form a meaningful and active approach to the development of creativity. Based on the development of students' creativity skills, it is appropriate to pay special attention to the development of their specialized, i.e., pedagogical creativity competence, in which it is appropriate to make extensive use of modern information and communication technologies, innovative strategies, interactive educational methods and technologies.

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